

The challenges of Sustainable Development (SD) – Case of Morocco

Les défis du développement durable (DD) – Cas du Maroc

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Abstract

The term "sustainable development" refers to a common philosophy that promotes the balance of human interests, economic development, environmental sustainability and the preservation of social and societal balances. Surprisingly, the path we could take, as well as what has been reflected in various media, would not limit long-term growth to the environmental cliff.

Much has been written about sustainable development. Many social actors, institutions and organizations are calling for it. The environment is a public good that everyone enjoys without necessarily paying the price. This "free" approach has resulted in waste of natural resources and climate change that challenges our sustainable development opportunities. The objective of this article is to highlight the various challenges and concerns that hinder Morocco's long-term development.

This study reflects on the foundations and specificities of sustainable growth as a general solution to maintain the long-term viability of our environments, habitats and economies.

Keys words: Sustainable development; environmental dimension; economic dimension; social dimension; fundamentals and peculiarities of sustainable development.

Résumé

Le terme "développement durable" fait référence à une philosophie commune qui favorise l'équilibre des intérêts humains, le développement économique, la durabilité environnementale et la préservation des équilibres sociaux et sociétaux. Étonnamment, la voie que nous pourrions emprunter, ainsi que ce qui a été reflété dans divers médias, ne limiterait pas la croissance à long terme à la falaise environnementale.

Le développement durable a fait couler beaucoup d'encre. De nombreux acteurs sociaux, institutions et organisations le réclament. L'environnement est un bien public dont chacun profite sans nécessairement en payer le prix. Cette approche "gratuite" a entraîné un gaspillage des ressources naturelles et un changement climatique qui remet en cause nos possibilités de développement durable. L'objectif de cet article est de mettre en évidence les différents défis et préoccupations qui entravent le développement à long terme du Maroc.

Cette étude réfléchit sur les fondements et les spécificités de la croissance durable comme solution générale pour maintenir la viabilité à long terme de nos environnements, habitats et économies.

Mots clés : Développement durable; dimension environnementale; dimension économique; dimension sociale; fondements et spécificités du développement durable.

Introduction

*“We do not inherit the land from our ancestors.
We borrow it from our children.”
Antoine de Saint-Exupéry*

Much has been written about the theme of long-term development. Several personalities of the company, as well as organizations and unions, are present. Environmental safety is a universal value that everyone can benefit from without having to pay for it. This "crisis" has resulted in a loss of natural resources and a climate revolution, making our ability to grow indefinitely questionable. The objective of this article is to highlight the different challenges and concerns that hinder Morocco's long-term development.

Since the early 1970s, global environmental concerns have continued to grow. They follow industrial development, urbanization, the integration of accidents and major natural disasters, or climate change.

Air pollution of water and soil, the gradual depletion of certain resources and energy sources, the increase in the volume of waste, etc. alert us to the need for better environmental protection and controlled economic growth. This overall perception of environmental degradation has been accompanied by an awareness of the development gaps between northern and southern countries. The scope of SD analysis has expanded in both space and time.

The appropriation in 1987 of the Brundtland Report by the World Commission on Environment and Development of His Majesty King Mohammed VI. This responsibility was at that point clear in 1992, when His Majesty, actually Crown Prince at that point, introduced at the Rio Summit his "Vision of the essentials for the development of another model of society". From that point forward, this obligation to the crucial standards is a significant advance towards the formalization of this idea and will cherish the term supportable turn of events.

Although sustainable development was a relatively unknown idea until the second half of the 20th century, it quickly gained importance in the face of the multiplication of these ecological crises and their consequences on human societies. As scientific knowledge advances on issues such as the ozone layer, global warming or biodiversity loss, the international community has recognized the need to find an economic model that can meet our needs without destroying our ecosystem.

The Sustainable Development Goals give us the way to a superior and more supportable future for all. They react to the worldwide difficulties we face, including those identified with

destitution, imbalance, environment, natural debasement, success, harmony and equity. The objectives are interconnected and, to abandon nobody, it is critical to meet every one of them, and every one of their objectives, by 2030."

The challenges of SD in Morocco

The three pillars of SD are environmental protection, economic growth and social equity.

The environment in Morocco is in constant degradation and natural resources are steadily diminishing: air and water pollution, deforestation, wind and water erosion of soils, desertification, biodiversity threatened, among others.

Among the many challenges related to the environment, the Collectif Démocratie et Modernité has chosen to limit the debate to three themes: the first concerns health and the environment, the second waste management, and the third concerns the problem of water.

A protected environment is the key to better health (WHO, 1999).

The environment can become a source of danger through natural phenomena, economic activities (energy, industry), human activities (homes, workplaces). The vectors between the environment and man are air, water, the food chain, ionizing radiation.

In Morocco, air pollution in urban areas has been studied in certain agglomerations. It is partly linked to road traffic, the rest to peri-urban industrial settlements. Measurements of ozone, carbon monoxide, sulphur dioxide and nitrogen dioxide are above acceptable standards. This pollution is responsible for a significant increase in respiratory infections, asthma attacks, bronchitis, as well as an increase in the conjunctivitis index. The industries that contribute the most to air pollution are energy plants (thermal power plants and oil refineries), chemical, textile, food, electrical and electronic, metal and metallurgical industries.

This paper is a reflection on sustainable growth, which is a new approach to ensuring the long-term sustainability of our environments, ecosystems and economies. Consequently, our research problem is the following :

What Sustainable Development in Developing Countries and Morocco ?

Our article is based on four interesting paving stones, first we focus on the origins of sustainable development, second we talk about the challenges, definitions and measures of sustainable development, At the same time we are defining the dimensions of sustainable development and the last one is based on the principles of sustainable development.

1. Conceptual Theoretical Framework : The Fundamentals of Sustainable Development :

1.1. SD Definition and History

The notion of sustainable development is now an integral part of the discourse of the majority of leaders and development policies. However, this concept emerged after a long reflection on the adverse effects of human activity on the environment. The first major international conferences on the effects of human activity on the environment, which date back to the late nineteenth century, focused mainly on the protection of certain environmental aspects, more specifically a particular species.

Table 1 : First international environmental conventions

1885	Berlin Convention on Rhine Salmon
1895	Paris Conference on Bird Protection
1900	London Conference on the Protection of Birds
1902	Paris International Conference on Bird Protection
1910	8th International Congress of Zoology in Graz (Austria). Creation of a provisional committee to study the question of the protection of nature in the world.
1923	First international non-governmental congress for the protection of nature (fauna, flora, natural monuments) in Paris.

Source : Veyret, Y. Le développement durable, édlttons Sedes, Paris, p. 432

We can classify sustainable development into two categories:

- Concerns about natural resources are overexpressed in the economy (since the eighteenth century with Malthus) "The economy of looting", for example, is a German study of the nineteenth century." Stop development," it was said in the twentieth century.
- Ecology: responsibility to protect the natural ecosystem, fauna and flora in order to properly exploit the natural resources... The politics of national parks (movements of English Puritans in the United States in the nineteenth century, creation of parks, places of preservation of the natural environment perceived as being of divine origin, facing the man, evil and that destroys this beautiful nature).

Table 2 : Different definitions of sustainable development

Body	Definition
IUCN International Union for Conservation of Nature (1980)	“A development that provides for real improvements in the quality of life of humans and at the same time maintains the vitality and diversity of the Earth. The goal is sustainable development. To this day, this notion seems utopian, yet it is achievable.”
UN United Nations (1987)	“advancement that addresses the issues of the present without trading off the capacity of people in the future to meet their own. ”
IUCN, UNEP United Nations Environment Programme, WWF	“Development that improves the quality of human life while respecting the capacity of its ecosystem.” (Caring for the Earth: a Strategy for Sustainable Living)
Earth Council, 1997	“Live fairly, in accordance with natural means”
Ignacy Sachs	“The five dimensions of sustainability or ecodevelopment are: the social dimension (other growth, other vision of society), the economic dimension (better distribution and management of resources, greater efficiency), ecological (minimising damage to natural systems), spatial (urban-rural balance, spatial planning), cultural (plurality of local solutions that respect cultural continuity)”
European Union	“A policy and strategy aimed at ensuring the continuity of economic and social development over time, respect for the environment without compromising the natural resources essential to human activity (5th Community Environmental Programme, towards sustainable development, 93-2000) ”
European Commission	“A regulation and strategy whose aim is to ensure the continuity over time of social and economic development, while respecting the environment and without compromising the natural resources that are essential to human activity.”
OECD Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2001)	“A coordinated set of participatory processes for continuous progress in the areas of analysis, debate, capacity building, planning and resource mobilization, and reconciling economic objectives, society’s social and environmental, where to proceed, if necessary, to arbitrations”
The World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD)	“Three pillars: economic growth, ecological balance and social progress. Continued sustainable development is good for trade (“business”) and trade is good for sustainable development.”

Source : Article de la Rubrique Adéquations

1.2. SD Dimensions (Eco, Social and Environmental)

Most executive conversations and sustainable development plans include a discussion on sustainable development. This is an international concept that has emerged from extensive research on the adverse effects of human activity on the environment.

In the early 1960s, the first criticisms of the method of productivist growth surfaced. The Club of Rome, created in 1968 and composed of industrialists from 53 countries, is at the forefront of this movement. This club brings together professors, scientists, economists, humanists, national and international officials. They are concerned about the various environmental challenges facing urban and developing societies, such as deforestation, sustainable development, economic growth, degradation of raw materials, etc.

In 1971, the 24 part nations of the Organization for Economic Co-activity and Development (OECD) received the "polluter pays" guideline. This philosophy is based on the ethics of duty, which aims to allow each economic actor to take into account the negative externalities of his activity.

The notion of sustainable development is now an integral part of the discourse of the majority of leaders and development policies. However, this concept emerged after a long reflection on the adverse effects of human activity on the environment. The first major international conferences on the effects of human activity on the environment, which date back to the late nineteenth century, focused mainly on the protection of certain environmental aspects, more specifically a particular species.

Sustainable development is described by three main interdependent pillars: an economic pillar, a social pillar and an environmental pillar. The philosophy behind integrating these three components into a single model is that the environment, the atmosphere and society are all interconnected to create a more sustainable balance. Therefore, we must never limit ourselves to the preconceived idea that sustainability is only about preserving the environment.

The most common graphical representation of the relationship between these three pillars is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Dimensions of sustainable development

Source : *Développement durable et territoires* [En ligne], Dossier 3 | 2004, mis en ligne le 07 novembre 2004,

1.3. SD Objectives and Principles

The three pillars of SD are environmental protection, economic growth and social equity. The environment in Morocco is constantly deteriorating and natural resources are steadily shrinking: air and water pollution, deforestation, wind and water erosion, desertification, threatened biodiversity, among others. Among the many challenges related to the environment, the Collectif Démocratie et Modernité has chosen to limit the debate to three themes : the first concerns health and the environment, the second concerns waste management, and the third concerns water. A protected environment is the key to better health (WHO, 1999). The environment can become a source of danger through natural phenomena, economic activities (energy, industry), human activities (dwellings, workplaces).

The vectors between the environment and man are air, water, the food chain, ionizing radiation. In Morocco, air pollution in urban areas has been studied in certain agglomerations. It is partly linked to road traffic, the rest to peri-urban industrial settlements. Measurements of ozone, carbon monoxide, sulphur dioxide and nitrogen dioxide are above acceptable standards. This pollution is responsible for a significant increase in respiratory infections, asthma attacks, bronchitis, as well as an increase in the conjunctivitis index. The industries that contribute the most to air pollution are energy plants (thermal power plants and oil refineries), chemical, textile, food, electrical and electronic, metal and metallurgical industries.

1.4. SD system : instance of Morocco

The Kingdom of Morocco is focused on gathering the difficulties of the 21st century by making maintainable advancement a genuine social undertaking and another model of improvement

under the edified drive of His Majesty King Mohammed VI. This duty was by then clear in 1992, when His Majesty, really Crown Prince by then, presented at the Rio Summit his "Vision of the basics for the improvement of another model of society". Starting now and into the foreseeable future, this commitment to the urgent guidelines Phase I : Economic and Social Upgrading (1992-2000) Outgoing from its Structural Adjustment Program (SAP) directed mutually with the International Monetary Fund (IMF: 1981-1994), Morocco that point forward, this obligation to the crucial standards of feasible advancement has been reflected in progressive changes pointed toward building a strong establishment for financial turn of events, improve social conditions and speed up the speed of natural accomplishments through both preventive and remedial measures. The advancement of Morocco's direction over the previous 20 years, as far as the development of a general public task dependent on feasible turn of events, can be summed up in three significant stages as follows:

Phase I : Economic and Social Upgrading (1992-2000) Outgoing from its Structural Adjustment Program (SAP) directed mutually with the International Monetary Fund (IMF: 1981-1994), Morocco has started an arrangement of progression of its economy and fortified certain key mechanical areas for send out, vital for the exchange balance, while zeroing in on the tertiarization of its economy. Simultaneously, an enormous extent of public venture has been focused on significant social activities pointed toward opening up the rustic world, for example, PERG (Program d'Electrification Rurale Généralisée), PNRR (Program National des Routes Rurales) or PAGER (Program d'Approvisionnement Groupé en Eau Potable des Populations Rurales). This first stage is likewise set apart by significant changes of the monetary and money related area specifically, just as the marking of the principal international alliance with the European Union in 1995, denoting the kickoff of the economy to the worldwide.

Phase II : Implementation of the principal switches and speed increase of improvement (2000-2011) This is a period of speed increase of institutional and lawful changes, particularly on the social level with the change of the family code. Additionally, the execution of the National Initiative for Human Development has set up a genuine social designing in a cycle of interest. At the financial level, sectoral procedures offer more prominent perceivability and take into account more focused on speculations. The approach of transparency is likewise speeding up with the section into power of international alliances with the United States of America (2004), the Greater Arab Zone (2005), Turkey (2006) and the Agadir arrangements (2007). The

ecological column is additionally reinforced with the reception of the principal major natural laws like Law 11-03 on Environmental Protection and Development, Law 12-03 on Environmental Impact Assessments, Air Pollution Act 13-03, or fortifying ecological activity.

Phase III : Constitutional change and operationalization of reasonable turn of events (ac. 2011) 2011 imprints a defining moment in the acknowledgment of the social task. Sectoral approaches show a few limits, particularly for the joining of cross-cutting issues that characterize maintainability. The accompanying key dates measure the advancement of the systematization of economical improvement in Morocco.

2. Economic Analysis of Sustainable Development and Means of Delivery: Key Challenges and Issues

2.1. The foundations of sustainable development

The SNDD, an instrument for the assembly and operationalization of submitted approaches Morocco has, since its freedom, set up significant arranging, which has focused on over 40 years, financial and social turn of events and gave it genuine resources for shape its future. The different activities, at first dispatched to manage crises (financial, social, ecological, institutional) 10 National Sustainable Development Strategy 2030 should now be merged around a general public venture, needed by His Majesty King Mohammed VI and conveyed by every one of the living powers of the Moroccan country. The intentional sectoral arrangements executed today add to the improvement of Morocco, with various levels of manageability. They were created under the duty of the different departmental authorities and in counsel with all partners. They are acceptable rules for activity for the distinctive clerical offices and areas concerned; however are neither orchestrated nor composed by a consistent idea that would decipher Morocco's consideration in a dynamic of human turn of events and natural security that would empower it to confront the difficulties of the century. Also, public administration of manageable turn of events, for recorded reasons in Morocco, as in numerous nations, is generally determined by the organization responsible for maintainable turn of events. The entire issue of the SNDD is in this manner, from one viewpoint, to reinforce rationality on a manageable premise, and to stretch out economical improvement administration to every applicable entertainer, with the goal that the vision of advancement is pervaded by manageability and shared. Furthermore, during the checking stage, the particular destinations that this technique should meet have been formed. The NSDS ought to be:

- An operational procedure dependent on the truth of the field and the projects at present being carried out.
- A procedure that makes it conceivable to improve collaborations between the different government activities, common society and financial administrators;
- A methodology that is certainly not an alternate forward-glancing vision comparable to the essential decisions previously made, however that looks to incorporate components of supportability into submitted approaches.

The lucidness of the National Sustainable Development Strategy depends on 4 standards A National Sustainable Development Strategy should meet various core values, set by the Government to guarantee consistency in its plan. Thusly, the standards used to build up this methodology were the...

Principle 1 : worldwide consistence The Kingdom of Morocco has marked and sanctioned the principle International and Regional Conventions identifying with the climate and practical turn of events. The National Strategy for Sustainable Development is in accordance with worldwide prescribed procedures and takes up at any rate the difficulties on which the Kingdom is submitted as far as manageable turn of events; to be specific: the battle against environmental change, fighting desertification, securing biodiversity, and so forth

Principle 2 : consistence with the standards of the National Environmental and Sustainable Development Charter, Framework Act 99-12 The operational measures illustrated in the National Sustainable Development Strategy are consistent with the principles of the Act-Box 99-12 to include :

- Principle of integration;
- Principle of territoriality;
- Principle of solidarity;
- Precautionary principle;
- Principle of prevention;
- Principle of responsibility;
- Principle of participation.

Principle 3 : Stakeholder engagement

The National Sustainable Development Strategy is over every one of the a ceaseless cycle that submits entertainers to change their conduct according to conventional turn of events. Along

these lines, it sets focuses for 2017-2030 and recognizes operational measures on which partners are submitted.

By far most of these actions have effectively been recognized or even started by the public specialists, so the SNDD will simply look after their observing and execution. Different measures are new and react to manageability gives that have not been thought of. Once embraced by the Government in June 2018, this system turned into a responsibility of all, as per the arrangements of the Framework Law 99-12.

Principle 4 : an operational procedure

The procedure is expected to be operational dependent on the techniques, plans and projects at present being carried out. The procedure is not the slightest bit a break with the improvement decisions made by the Kingdom. It depends on concrete and operational measures.

2.2. The difficulties of SD in Morocco

Despite endeavors to moor the standards of economical turn of events, Morocco actually faces difficulties to address its difficulties: the proceeded with expansion in energy or food costs, unfavorable impacts identified with environmental change, loss of organic variety, consumption of characteristic assets and enhancement of social imbalances. These difficulties might have impeded Morocco's turn of events, however by benefiting from the significant changes attempted in ongoing many years, the Kingdom has emphatically sped up the speed of its accomplishments giving the country a noticeable and perceived blast because of the associative and controlled lead of a few significant underlying activities:

- Strengthening of the economic framework and liberal orientation: Debt reduction and maintenance of macroeconomic balances; creation of multiple free trade areas (EU, USA, Arab Countries, Turkey).
- Mise en service de grandes infrastructures de transport avec la politique des grands chantiers (autoroutes, ports, aéroports).
- Implementation of voluntary sectoral policies: Plan Maroc Vert (agriculture), Plan Émergence I, II et Accélération Industrielle (industrie), Vision 2010 et Vision 2020 (tourism), Plan Rawaj (commerce), Morocco Digital Plan (new information and communication technologies), Plan Halieutis (Maritime Fisheries), Logistics Strategy 2030, Morocco Innovation Strategy, Energy Strategy, etc.

- Guarantee of its water and food security: dam policy, Law 10-95 on water, use of unconventional waters, Plan Maroc Vert for the agricultural sector, promotion of agricultural research, etc.
- Implementation of an arrangement to advance environmentally friendly power and energy productivity: Strengthening of the administrative and institutional system, monetary motivating forces, Solar Plan, Wind Energy Plan, and so on
- Implementation of a natural overhauling strategy: standardization of reasonable turn of events (National Charter for the Environment and Sustainable Development), fortifying of the administrative system, National Sanitation Program (PNA), National Program for Household Waste Management (PNDM), Creation of the Moroccan Center for Clean Production (CMPP).
- Promotion of human turn of events and social fortitude: National Initiative for Human Development, Implementation of the RAMED (Medical Assistance Scheme) to serve the denied populace, implem improvement of pre- and neonatal care, generalization of schooling, reform of education, reform and empowerment of the University, access to drinking water in rural areas (Programme d'Approvisionnement Groupé en Eau Potable des Populations Rurales - PAGER) and electrification of rural (Global Rural Electrification Programme -PERG), National Rural Roads Program... Despite the efforts made, many issues remain to be addressed in order for the country to lay the foundations for sustainable development.
- Water, whose scarcity threatens life and slows down the economy, is subjected to multiple pressures and becomes even rarer and polluted.
- Biodiversity, both in the terrestrial domain and its wetlands or its coastline, as well as in the coastal and marine domain, is also subject to very strong pressures, to degradation, predation, dysfunction, unprecedented losses and losses, without the programmes committed achieving their objectives.
- Energy, imported, is increasingly expensive and variations in its cost hinder economic development.
- Cities are growing without urban services meeting the vital needs of urban populations.
- The improvement of the education system is too slow and the unemployment rate of 9% on average, which particularly affects young graduates, is worrying. Employment is marked by the predominance of informal and low-skilled forms.
- The pension system is a threatening risk factor: the fund deficit is expected to be 4% of GDP by 2040 if reform is not carried out.

- The government deficit, which reached more than 7% of GDP in 2013, and the liquidity crisis can threaten long-term macroeconomic balances.
- The trade deficit of 8% in 2012 is no longer offset by the income of Moroccan residents abroad, tourism or foreign direct investment. This leads to a loss of the country's competitiveness, particularly in terms of unit labour costs. As a result, Morocco deducts from the already lower domestic liquidity to acquire the foreign exchange needed to settle its imports.
- The operation of the Compensation Fund, whose level of subsidies has reached 5% of GDP, needs to be reviewed to support disadvantaged populations and to direct its action towards direct aid rather than through an undifferentiated system of subsidies.
- Finally, true economic governance is lacking in the sense that the national tax system is not yet satisfactory and remains an open project, public regulations are not adapted and the informal sector still occupies a considerable place. These distortions illustrate the reality of a “two-speed Morocco” both economically efficient in certain sectors, with grey areas very threatening for the future, social and geographical inequalities still marked and a degradation of the Kingdom's natural resources, despite the efforts made to protect them.

This situation is likely to grow if we do not act and take tangible and tangible actions to change our development patterns.

2.3. SD : what solution ?

It is in this changing context that HIS MAJESTY KING MOHAMMED VI has called upon the Government, in the 2009 and 2010 Speeches from the Throne, to develop a draft National Charter for the Environment and Sustainable Development and an integrated action plan formalized in an A framework that should be a real reference for our country's public policies in this area. Indeed, HIS MAJESTY THE KING stressed the need for a «model of development and democracy that We want specifically Moroccan». This model, which leads to harmonious development, is based on sustained economic growth, which will strengthen our social solidarity policy.

It is also intended to promote the achievement of sustainable development, taking into account the imperatives of environmental protection. It is also a model whose methodology is based on the rules of good governance.” Extract from the Speech of SM King Mohammed VI The King will deliver on this occasion the words of “green growth” and “green development”. HIS MAJESTY THE KING MOHAMMED VI thus confirmed his desire to develop the Kingdom according to the principles of sustainable development. The 2011 Constitution provided a new

impetus to this process by enshrining sustainable development as a right for all citizens and introducing new instruments of democratic governance. It is within this framework that a National Sustainable Development Strategy (SNDD) has been developed through a broad consultation with all stakeholders : the public sector, private operators and civil society. The SNDD thus represents this commitment to operationalize sustainable development at the scale of the Kingdom. It must be an integrative and unifying project that meets the needs and aspirations of society.

The SNDD is therefore not just another strategy, but the logical and strategic framework that enables coherence and synergy between programmes, plans and sectoral policies from a sustainability perspective and in the spirit of participation of all. It must thus draw a project of society, a future of the Kingdom respectful of the value of the territories, its natural and cultural heritage, the aspirations of its youth and the rights of future generations. The SNDD is also a concrete response to Morocco's international commitments and a way of gaining recognition from donors and the international community for a country that has understood and integrated both the challenges and complexities of modernity and aspirations of peoples to shared governance.

All the components of good governance of sustainable development are thus brought together and are valid for both national and international governance: the three pillars of sustainable development, its interdisciplinarity, the need for it to be implemented at all levels, for it to be carried by managers, for efficiency, the requirement for scientific exchanges, public participation and the periodic evaluation of its implementation. It nevertheless acts in this outline of definition of both governance in general, and governance of sustainable development. It seems essential to us to distinguish the two, because both the good governance of a country, and the effective governance of sustainable development in that same country, mark a good understanding of the requirements induced by sustainable development. Today, good governance is defined as the allocation and management of national resources characterized by participation, transparency, accountability, rule of law, efficiency and fairness. It is a process that involves "long-term construction and involves a more or less slow change in the mental and organizational structures of governance." Taking into account the changes in perspective required in the context of the operationalization of sustainable development, The revision of the modes of governance is considered as a prerequisite for citizen participation. In other words, the effective foundation for achieving sustainable development lies in the prior building of

democratic governance, without which sustainable development remains a technocratic concept unrelated to development, which is the target of governments and citizens, especially in countries where large pockets of poverty remain.

Perspectives and contributions of the research

As everyone can attest, allusions to sustainable development have been widely disseminated in recent years in politics, the media and industry, as well as in research and education. As the number of allusions increases, so does the criticism that has followed this notion since its inception in the 1980s. We recognize the risk of opportunism in the allusion to a broad and consensual notion that promises a good revival without leading to reforms adapted to the difficulties encountered (Smouts, 2005; Aubertin and Vivien, 2006).

These allusions do, however, contribute to changing the structure of certain political and professional fields. The aim of this article is to examine some of these developments in the academic sphere of research and higher education through the prism of scientific disciplines. Higher education, as well as the training and production of researchers, is heavily influenced by scientific fields, so we recommend determining the precise location of sustainable development in relation to these structures, as these interactions will impact its inscription and potential influence in the academic environment.

In addition to the aforementioned discussions about the scope of different words, it should be noted that even this basic delineation is not guaranteed. For example, one of the most active areas around the term today, the environment, is not the fundamental notion for large companies referring to sustainable development: it is "social or societal responsibility" that is at risk, with a triptych created by the "environmental," the "social" and the "economic." Moreover, in some sectors of European politics and administration, where the crucial method of impact studies (on sustainable development) of directives and policies puts economic, social and environmental analyses on the same level, the same is true (COP 26).

The central concept of Local Agenda 21 is participatory government rather than environmental conservation. In the field of research, a key report on Morocco's relationship with sustainable development states: "It is useful to emphasize the distinctive features resulting from the conjunction of the ideas of development and sustainability: long time, extended space, interconnections" (Hautcur, 2003).

Limitations of the research

In any event, changes might occur in a number of ways in the fundamental textures of scientific production and education. We attempted to come up with instances based on disciplinary differences, such as reorganizations at work and others that would be beneficial. This diverse nature of the concretizations, together with their inclusion in a transversal reference to disciplines, seems to be extremely current data on the condition of sustainable development implementation in academia. We've argued that "specialties" in sustainable development tied to specific degrees would better reflect current trends than the creation of a prospective discipline in this field.

It's not simple to maintain the proper distance from the symbolic power of sustainable development's recurrent invocations of innovation. We cannot continue to be deaf to the clear adjustments that are necessary in the response to some large and little challenges. But we can't expect the multiplication of connections and topics attempted to embrace the numerous features of a concept, despite the problems we've seen, to provide the ideal approach on its own. The position advocated here is a fine examination of the irruption and influence of sustainable development on these academic scenes using existing intellectual tools, thus reserving time for a case-by-case examination before subscribing to the general affirmation of structuring innovation that it can carry.

Conclusion

The vast majority of countries around the world are committed to adopting policies that encourage "sustainable development". Many large companies, both public and private, report on their long-term development commitments. Finally, there is a growing general understanding of environmental protection and natural resource management. Although the concept of sustainable development has become widespread, it is nevertheless difficult to give a concise definition that takes into account the various points of view that this area covers.

Growth is "sustainable" if it is designed in such a way that benefits are passed on to future generations. Environmentally friendly, economically equitable and productive development is necessary for long-term growth. The land must be seen as a condition, the social as a target and the economy as a means to achieve it. Citizens, municipal councils, states, businesses, organizations, scientists and associations: all people must work together to respond and function in the face of the challenges of the earth and humanity.

At this stage we propose the following recommendations:

- To develop a longitudinal study in the future, a study resulting from the monitoring of a population or a phenomenon over time according to a starting event. The objective of longitudinal research is to map a development over a specific period. A comparison can be made between the start and end measure (and intermediate measures) of a particular phenomenon. Thus, the longitudinal study is conceptually opposed to the cross-sectional study which is interested in a phenomenon at time t . Thus, time is a determining criterion for observing a phenomenon in the framework of a longitudinal study according to the following conditions: the data collected cover at least two distinct periods and the subjects are identical or at least comparable from one period to the next
- Extend research on another concept of sustainable development based on research related to a new concept invented over time
- Establish a benchmarking approach with another country: sustainable development differs from one country to another.

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